

FUTURE PROSPECT OF ETHICS TEACHING: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Ethics is the principles and standards of moral behavior that deals with what people ought to do and what not. Recently, crime grows up rapidly which can be alert of disappearance values, morals and ethics. Ethics can work to resolve this because ethics is the foundation of personal well being. Ethics can be learned from family, religion, institute and society, the question is can ethics be taught in classroom and how. Teaching Ethics is a contemporary issue as many tertiary institutes are teaching ethics by different ways and methods. To discover the answers of several questions related to ethics teaching author devoted to this study and the objectives of this paper are to discover whether ethics can be learned and taught , ways of teaching ethics and opinions on teaching ethics. By the nature, it is a descriptive research focused on both qualitative and quantitative approaches where the tools are reflection paper, observation and survey questionnaire. Sample groups are undergraduate students from two private universities and sample size is 300. Findings of the study stated that family, society, religion and education contribute to develop rational justification and practice of ethical behaviors where parents, teachers and the person himself are the key group of actors. Maximum students (89% and 92%) of X and Y universities declared, ethics can be learned where approximately 76% and 80% pupil were positive about the possibility of teaching ethics The study also discovered an ethics course at least insert and improve knowledge of ethics within learners.

Keywords: Ethics, Ethics Teaching, Comparative Study

INTRODUCTION

Is corruption black or white for the cost of development? Is cheating is good or bad for helping others? Is stealing right or wrong? Is lying ethical to save human life? To answer this category of thousand questions we need a concrete understanding of rightness and wrongness or goodness and badness. A child likes to do thing what gives him pleasure and that pleasant thing becomes good one to conduct for him as well as what gives him pain, he avoids. After some years, when he/she observers and understands, the task that he/she does are appreciated by others those are right and blameworthy task are wrong. The study of rightness and wrongness is known as ethics. Ethics refers to well-substantiated standards of right and wrong which prescribe what humans ought to do, generally in terms of rights, fairness, obligations, benefits of the society or specific virtues(Velasquez, Andre, Shanks, S.J., & J. Meyer, 2010). Now the question is, can ethics be taught and learned?

Collected hard evidence by the psychologists' answer is yes (Velasquez, Andre, Shanks, S.J., & J. Meyer, 2014); recently, the educationalist identify that they cannot teach ethics. The reason is what would be the curriculum or what should be taught (content) and what would be religious (spiritual) and cultural disagreements associated to ethics (Conroy & Emerson, 2004).In addition, there is a say that ethics is a personal matter and inappropriate to discussion in classroom situation. When an individual is in a decision making process, he needs to justify his action by defining right and wrong in an interpersonal frame. Conversely, measurement process of defining action by the features of ethics is impractical. Inadequate practice of ethics is present whereas an interpersonal ethics is

required fundamentally (R.Piper, C.Gentile, & Parks, 1993). Ethics should not be a private matter rather it should be within educational programs and deans of many business school rank ethics among the top five learning goals for their programs (Ryan & Bisson, 2011).

Ethics is the principles and standards of moral behavior that is accepted by society, “right” as opposed to “wrong” which is concerned with moral obligation, responsibility and social justice of all parties involved in the decision making process that have been understood by me while conducting ethics course in a private university in Bangladesh. From that period I was concentrated to discover the answers of several questions related to ethics teaching and I was devoted to this study.

ETHICS CURRICULUM: BANGLADESHI CONTEXT

In Bangladesh, ethics is a matter of considering as a subject in the field of medical science and education where medical ethics, history of medical ethics and ethics apply in medical practices are the subject areas (Bangladesh Medical & Dental Council (BM&DC), December 2008). Reality, very few private medical colleges have ethics as a subject. Correspondingly, in the ground of engineering universities, private and public universities have fewer scope than the previous. However, some of the private universities incorporated ethics as a cross cutting topic within the curriculum or at least an open credit course (If any student is interested, he can take) (B.Sc. in Electrical and Electronic Engineering (EEE), 2012); there ethical principles and applications are the main topics. On the other hand, the image is vivid in the BBA and MBA programs in Bangladeshi private and public universities. Many private universities like Southern University Bangladesh, Southeast University, Green University of Bangladesh, North South University etc have Ethics as a subject named Business Ethics and the components of the course are ethical theories (mostly teleology and deontology), application of ethics in business, ethical dilemma, ethical role of Business or CSR (UGC Bangladesh, 2009). Some of the universities have added Ethics as a compulsory course for all undergraduate students. Ethics is a separate credit course and mandatory course for BRAC University students titled as Ethics and Culture course and in the curriculum, ethical theories (consequentialism, cultural relativism, teleology, deontology, care ethics and justice), practical application (daily life ethical dilemmas and solution) and demonstration (Course Outline and Reading Materials of Ethics and Culture Course), these three areas are covered (BRAC University, 2014). Eastern University also has a credit course but mandatory course for all students where ethical theories are the main parts (Rob, 2014).

STUDY RATIONALITY

In recent times, while in far and wide law exists but crime grows up rapidly. This scenario can be aware of disappearanceⁱⁱ values, ⁱⁱⁱ morals and ethics. Many social issues like capitalistic society, enormous growth of using technology transform truth, beauty, goodness and faith into contradictions. Ethics can work to resolve this as ethics is the foundation of personal well being which we have lost now-a-days (Videnovic, 2003). Ethics can learn from family, religion, institute and society where the question is can ethics be taught and how. Teaching Ethics is a contemporary issue as many tertiary institutes are teaching ethics indifferent ways and methods. Which methods and modules are appropriate? Which level we need to consider for teaching ethics? If we cannot teach ethics then how it will be created within learners, this sort of doubts calls for discovery. A uniformed course or integrated course inside the curriculum is also necessary if we are prepared to teach ethics. For this perspective, opinion on teaching ethics, students' readiness and possibility of course implication are required to find out. A survey results indicate that Ethics courses may be resulting in better ethical decision making. Perhaps alerting students to ethical violations is making them more aware of their decisions in the workplace. The results indicate that requiring an ethics course does make an immediate (albeit perhaps short term) difference in ethical decision making or in assessing potential

ethical/unethical behavior (Violet Rogers, 2008).

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Socrates (500 BC) stated, “Ethics consists of knowing what we ought to do,” and such knowledge, synonymously ethics, can be taught. Ever since the times of the Greeks, men have been fascinated by the moral faculty of the human mind. The human mind is a mysterious contraption. It has the capability of learning and retaining certain materials. Ethics is the philosophical discipline that focuses on ^{iv}morality and moral behavior. From the sophists to institutions like Harvard University, ethics is provided as a course, in the hopes of creating an integrated and holistic tertiary curriculum that will mold students into model, global citizens. However, in the debacles of Enron, World com and Abu Ghraib, the expectation of ethical behavior being taught were greatly dimmed (Bowden & Smythe, 2008).

The timeless philosophical debate of all mankind is centered around on one single question; can ethics be taught or not? Socrates considered ethics of being consisted of knowing what to do, and that type of knowledge can be taught (Velasquez, Andre, Shanks, S.J., & J. Meyer, 2014). Although his position on this issue was taken 2500years ago, modern psychological studies agree with his claim, especially Kohlberg’s moral development theory. Kohlberg found that a person’s moral development is gradually accumulated over the years and further enhanced with formal education. He classified three levels of moral development: pre-conventional, conventional and post-conventional. Many factors contribute to a person’s development through the stages, with education being the most crucial. Kohlberg saw his subjects, who took ethics courses during their tertiary education; eventually reach the post-conventional stage, where they were able to execute the powers of their moral faculties accordingly (Velasquez, Andre, Shanks, & Meyer, 1987). Harvard psychologist Kohlberg (1958) argued that ethics is a life-long process; he too agreed that those are only the first couple of stages of an individual’s moral development and that the next stage is on a post conventional level that has to be stimulated by education. It is safe to say that whether, or not, ethics can be taught in a classroom can be brought down to two components- the time and the content of the course. Psychologist James R. Rest (1982) supported the idea that ethics can be learned through continuing education.

A group of researchers (Martin, Gupta and Cowell,2008) of the university of North Carolina at Chapel-Hill described in their article named “Ethical Behavior in Accounting : some Evidence from USA” that student responses on “should ethics be taught as a separate course in a curriculum” were inconsistent with the current approaches and application in academics .According to the statistics, most of them thought that was no need for ethics to be taught a separate course, while only 22% thought that it would be useful. The evidence said that ethics education is important because it can facilitate a person’s moral reasoning, right decision making skills.

A group of faculty members (Yesemin Zengin Karabrahimoglu and others) of the Izmir University of Economics described in their article named Ethical behavior in accounting: some evidence from Turkey in 2009 that students’ responses on “should ethics be taught as a separate course in a curriculum” were same as the previous findings. According to the students, 39.0% considered that a separate ethics course was unnecessary while 24.4% were uncertain and 36.6% thought that it would be valuable (Karabrahimoglu, Erdener, & Var, 2009).

Right and wrong can vary with culture, legal rules and social lives. There are contradictory opinions on the necessity to teach ethics institutionally. 90 percent of American business schools keep ethics as a course, although the seriousness and effectiveness of curriculum in these courses are ambiguous. There are experts who consider ethics as a course is useless with existence of law, as well as they are not flawless. There are various aspects the instruction has to study (Ryan & Bisson, 2011).

Opportunities to face the real life challenges, assisting them in such activities is one vital task of the instructor. We have to encourage the pupils for a better skill and response to ethical issues by everyday examples. Ethics course has

an influence over the students in better judgment and decision making. Other than depending on traditional methods of study, in class discussions, hypothetic situations can provide a better stress and implication on the student. The values, morals and philosophical orientation among other variables come into play as peoples' perception and filter the events. This fact can change the manner in which we can be teach ethics in a course as it is needed to discuss how one can make a distinction from what is important to that which is less so. Personal values, professional ideologies and social norms will affect the students' ethics too (Ryan & Bisson, 2011).All these areas have to be explored for practical life experience.

RESERCH QUESTION

The following questions had been considered as research questions for the study.

- a) Can ethics be learned?
- b) Can ethics be taught?
- c) Why ethics can be taught or cannot be taught?
- d) What is learners' judgment about teaching ethics?
- e) How it can be taught?
- f) Can ethics be taught by modules/course or integrated within curricula?

METHODOLOGY

To conduct the research, private universities were labeled in two categories X and Y. In X group where ethics is a general but compulsory credit course and Y group represents where ethics in not a course nor integrated within the curriculum. By the nature of the study, it is a descriptive research focused on both qualitative (reflection paper and observation) and quantative (survey questionnaire) approaches.

SAMPLING:

In this research, two universities were selected purposively from the X and Y groups. And for collecting quantitative data from students, 100 pupils were randomly selected from X private university where ethics has been taught within the curriculum and 100 students were randomly selected from Y private university where ethics is not taught by a course or curriculum. Consequently, in sampled group all types of students were there according to age, gender and department. For qualitative data collection, 100 students were randomly selected from X university. Total sample size of the research was 300.

DATA COLLECTION TOOLS & ANALYSIS METHOD:

Variety of data collection tools were used to gather sufficient and appropriate data for the study.

Survey by Questionnaire: The researcher followed a uniformed questionnaire for collecting data from the both private universities. Two Hundred participants were responded in the survey independently. The survey questionnaires had 6 questions in combination of multiple choices, low to higher order and open ended questions. Before took part in the survey, they were well informed about the process. To ensure fairness, the participants were instructed not to write their names and identification number.

Reflection Paper: To understand, explore and analysis the research questions specially why ethics can be taught or cannot be taught? What is learners' judgment about teaching ethics? how it can be taught? ; The authors collected students' reflection on the topic of "Can Ethics be taught" and reviewed relevant information. The written reflection papers were asked from the students of X University only as they have completed the Ethics course. Basically, the researcher who was an instructor for the ethics course assigned the reflection paper as an assignment to the students.

For this study, 100 randomly selected reflection papers took in to the account.

Empirical Observation: To have primary data, researcher also got opportunity to involve in conducting ethics course and observed the impact of learning ethics as a course, students’ judgments and reactions towards the course in the X University. The researcher was being neutral during this procedure. By acquiring practical implication of ethics course, continues observations were conducted. To conduct the observation, ‘KAP study method was followed where three basic questions; Do the students gather knowledge about ethics, do the students have attitude to uphold those and do they practice ethics in their real life had to be answered. The research who was a classroom teacher for the sampled group had conducted the observations inside and outside the class.

Data Analysis Techniques: SPSS copyright version 17 computer packages and Microsoft Office Excel 2007 along with surveymonkey were applied to evaluate and interpret the quantitative date. Data which were collected by observations and reflection papers were analyzed through qualitative method.

ANALYSIS & REFLECTIVE DISCUSSION

To analysis the finding of qualitative and qualitative data, three major arenas such as Learning & Teaching Ethics, Approach of Ethics Teaching and Opinions of Ethics course have judged.

Table: 1

	Type of respond	Responses from X University (%)	Responses from Y University(%)
Can Ethics be Learned?	Yes	89	92
	No	11	8
Can Ethics be taught in classroom?	Yes	76	80
	No	24	20

Graph: 1

From Table and Graph: 1, maximum students (89% and 92%) of the both universities thought ethics can be learned where approximately 76% and 80% pupils of X and Y institute were positive about the possibility of teaching ethics. Around same percentages said, ethics can be taught in classroom.

Whereas, findings from reflection paper and observation from X University, 80% students said ethics cannot be a subject to teach in classroom and 20% stated that knowledge can be assembled. An opposite scenario is seen for teaching ethics in classroom. Learning ethics from classroom depends on the level and age of students, course content and design; 30% students have such kind of opinion. Several reasons are mentioned behind the issue. Practical natural of the course, Personal difference, Self realization, time and grading system of the course are pointed out. Most of the Learners about 50% said ethics is a matter of practice. We cannot be ethical by studying a course like people cannot be a dancer by a reading a dancing course. In contrast, students mentioned ethics is a subject of decision making skills (10%) and character building skills (12%) in the favor of teaching ethics in the classroom. They also argued by 10 % that everything can be learn so why not ethics.

Observations based on KAP methods, found satisfactory level of students gather knowledge from a ethics course nevertheless one third practice those during their semester over and above very few pupils have change their attitude towards practicing ethics.

Table: 2

Graph: 2

How Ethics can be Taught?	Approach	Responses from X University (%)	Responses from Y University (%)
	Practical/ Experience	13	12
	Theory	1	1
	Practical & Theory	81	82
	None	4	4
	Other (By Family, Religion, Society etc)	1	1

Graph: 2

From Graph: 2 and Table: 2, both of the universities’ students represented similar ideas about the way of ethics teaching where greatest number by more than 80% said ethics teaching likely theoretical and practical. This finding indicates people required knowledge of ethics and that can be done by introducing a course or integrated ethics in the curriculum. One tenth of participants asserted learning ethics by experience.

While, 40% students mentioned in their reflection papers that people learn ethics by experience. Correspondingly, 40% and 30% students said respectively parents and family play vital role to teach ethics. Religion (20%) and Society (10%) also have influencing role to educate ethics to human. One fourth learners declared ethics can be taught by schooling or by education in the tertiary level which depends on construction of the curriculum. The structural of the ethics curriculum has to be knowledge, practice and attitude based means course should provide suitable knowledge, scope of practice and modification of attitude.

Table 3 describes two aspect; opinion on introducing an ethics course and type of the course. More than two third participants are positive about initiating ethics course in their curriculum.

Table: 3

Introducing Ethics Course	Opinion	Responses from X University (%)	Responses from Y University (%)	What will be the type of Course for Ethics?	Opinion	Responses from X University (%)	Responses from Y University (%)
	Strongly agree	29	23		Mandatory but Non-credit course	15	12
	Agree	50	56		Credit course	29	36
	Neutral	14	15		Integrated course	28	25
	Disagree	6	5		Subject/ discipline	20	20
	Strongly disagree	1	1		None	7	7

For the both institutes, same percentages of students are neutral. If any university initiates ethics course, 20% students from both university said it can be a different subject discipline or faculty. Round 25-28% students articulated ethics is an integrated topic with all other courses in the respected discipline. A little dissimilarity is seen to introduce ethics as a credit course. X university responded by 29 % where Y university responded by 36%. Less than one fifth percentages of the both universities’ learners decided ethics is a mandatory but non credit course where one third said to make it credit course.

Qualitative data (reflection papers and observations from X university) revealed that half of the student body said introducing ethics course in the curriculum will be pointless and 5% students were entirely disagree with the notion. One fourth students felt that ethics might be introduced as a course and 15 % students do not have any opinions. Maximum pupils are disagreed to learn ethics by a course.

People’s personal views are different regarding teaching ethics by a course. Ethics classes provide knowledge and awareness as well as education influences ethics that are reflected by students. They mentioned the importance of

ethics in character building, decision making and logical thinking. Ethics also involves rational justification and for those reasons ethics might be taught. However, in the reflection paper students argued, can we make anybody to think rationally and logically? Simultaneously, knowledge promotes awareness although can we make anyone ethical by study a course. 35 % students are in doubt about this matter and 40 % students believed experience makes people ethical. Ethics is a matter of practice that reshapes behaviors and 20% learners emphasized on practice and 17% on modification of behavior. Students disputed about those practices and modifications are counted in the grading system of an ethics course. That is might be a reason for which 8 % students underlined process of ethics teaching. Ethics courses at least insure knowledge of ethics which was pointed out by 50% students. Some of the students also felt the role of family for learning ethics.

CONCLUSION

Ethics is the study of morality and moral behavior. Morality can never be forced inside a person. How a person is to interact with the people around him and his surrounding depends on his rational justification. It is either a by-born quality or it is nurtured with time without self realization. Is it possible to learn swimming by reading books? No matter how much we read about the skills, no matter how many different styles we know, we can never learn how to swim if we do not get in the water. Similarly, one cannot learn about ethics from books; he needs practical experience. Practical experience comes from our day to day lives. We observe the people around us and our society and we learn about ethics and morality in every step of the way which is disclosed by qualitative data of the study too. Even though numerical figures said positive about learning ethics by a course. To discover more depth arena, further research can be conducted on the topics like level of ethics course introducing, content of ethics course, process of teaching ethics, outcome of ethics course, grading of ethics course so on. Great philosophers like Aristotle, Socrates and Plato talked about ethics and the method of learning. Consequently, ethics come from experiences and depends on practice and to be ethical attitude is needed. Findings of the study stated family, society, religion and education contribute to develop rational justification and practice of ethical behaviors where parents, teachers and the person himself are the key group of actors. The study also discovered an ethics course at least insert and improve knowledge of ethics within learners. Though, the concern of evaluating practical implication and attitude of being ethical are in reservation. At the end, it can be said, a properly structured ethics course in the curriculum where knowledge gathering, practicing and having attitude to be ethical will be insured, can have a optimistic impact on future learners. A suggestion can be made by the observation that ethics teaching will be suitable in the tertiary level education as it requires logical and rational judgment and developmental psychology says after 18 years human brain can rationalize thing properly and effectively. However basic concepts can be introduced at early childhood.

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ⁱ Ethics is a study of rational justification moral principles, morality and moral behavior.

ⁱⁱ Values are a measure of the worth or importance a person attaches to something. Our values are often reflected in the way we live our lives. Values are our fundamental beliefs.

ⁱⁱⁱ Morals are values which we attribute to a system of beliefs, typically a religious system, but it could be a political system of some other set of beliefs. These values get their authority from something outside the individual- a higher being or higher authority (e.g. society).

^{iv} Morality (from the Latin moralities "manner, character, proper behavior") is the differentiation of intentions, decisions, and actions between those that are good or right and those that are bad, evil or wrong.

^v KAP study measures the Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of a community. It serves as an educational diagnosis of the community. The main purpose of this KAP study is to explore changes in Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of the community (Kaliyaperumal, March 2004).